

Research

Two-Step Photocurrent Generation through Band Tail States in GaPN-Based Intermediate Band Solar Cells

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Abstract: Two-step photocurrent generation due to the presence of pronounced band tail states in GaPN is reported by using two-wavelength excited photocurrent measurement technique. The results reveal that two-wavelength excitation significantly enhances the overall photocurrent generation due to the two-step photocurrent generation upon two-step two photon absorption in GaPN. The enhancement in the current density for the only below gap excitation and dual-wavelength excitation is observed to be 6×10^{-4} and 1.1×10^{-3} mA cm⁻², respectively. The absorption of below gap excitation light is found to increase the photocurrent density and external quantum efficiency due to the larger density of tail states. Finally, the simulation results enabled us to uncover the nature of enhancement in the current density, or ΔJ by the simultaneous illumination, the carrier dynamics in the intermediate state filling process as well as the effect of BGE light on the carrier relaxation time. The results demonstrated that electron relaxation time becomes 0.07 ns from 0.14 ns by the below gap excitation while hole relaxation time becomes 1.45 ns for the maximum photon flux.

Keywords: Below gap excitation, Dilute nitride semiconductor, GaPN, Solar cell, Two-step photocurrent generation

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Accepted: XX August, 2023; **Published:** XX August, 2023

How to cite this article: Abdul Qayoom, Shuhei Yagi, and Hiroyuki Yaguchi (2023). Two-Step Photocurrent Generation through Band Tail States in GaPN-Based Intermediate Band Solar Cells. *North American Academic Research*, 6(8), 20-31. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8300177>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

The exploitation of renewable energy is seen as an attempt to curb the environmental issue such as global warming, climate change and energy conservation for the sustainable development (Elliott, 2000). The light energy conversion has been achieved greatly using single junction solar cells for this purpose. It should be noted that single junction solar cells have achieved a prominent energy conversion efficiency of up to 28.8% by one sun irradiance (Green et al., 2020). This achievement approaches the theoretically attainable Shockley-Queisser limit (Shockley & Queisser, 1961). Photons with the same energy as the band gap are no waste in the energy conversion while photons with higher energies result in thermal loss. Likewise, photons with low energies cannot be absorbed and contribute to energy conversion (Shockley & Queisser, 1961; Hirst et al., 2010). The intermediate band solar cell (IBSC) (Luque and Marti, 1997) approach enlightens a way to the efficiency of about 63% over the SQ limit of approximately 40% for the concentrated light (Shockley &

Queisser, 1961). IBSCs utilize an additional band between the primary conduction band (CB) and valance band (VB) of materials called as the intermediate band (IB) to absorb photons having lower energies than the primary energy gap of materials (Luque and Marti, 1997; Marti, 2006; Luque and Marti, 2010). This concept enables additional photogenerated current density as the sum of photogenerated current density from the optical absorption between VB and IB, and between IB and CB. Even though theoretically a higher performance is expected, the realization of the formation of IB as well as the successful transitions through IB have been challenging (Luque and Marti, 1997; Marti, 2006; López et al., 2011). Successful implementation of IBSCs has been reported using highly mismatched alloys (HMA) (Wang et al., 2009; Tanaka et al., 2011; Tanaka et al., 2013; Tanaka et al., 2014), quantum dots (Ramiro et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2021)), and dilute magnetic materials (Raulot et al., 2005). Dilute nitride semiconductors among the HMA form IB because CB splits into E_+ and E_- sub bands due to nitrogen addition (Shan et al., 2000; Wu et al., 2002). Since the E_- sub band is located at lower energy than E_+ sub band, it is used as IB.

Similar split of the CB in one of the dilute nitrides, GaPN has also been witnessed. Furthermore, this material system has been reported to illustrate tail states either due to presence of nitrogen clusters (Chen et al., 2018) or distinct spatial distribution of nitrogen atoms within the crystal lattice (Yaguchi, 2022). Our recent work has showed a different approach to achieve the two-step photocurrent generation in $\text{GaP}_{1-x}\text{N}_x$ ($x = 0.75\%$) by exploiting the band tail states, effectively establishing them as the IB (Qayoom et al., 2023). This approach is in contrary to the conventional approach using E_- band as the IB in dilute nitride materials. We demonstrated a significant enhancement in photogenerated current by utilizing a wide range of below gap excitation (BGE). This study attempts to prolong and establish our assumption about BGE photon absorption through tail states by increasing the nitrogen concentration (N: 1.87%). The mechanism of two-step two photon absorption in GaPN using the band tail states as IB could potentially lead to IBSC technology achieving higher efficiency as expected. Therefore, we believe this concept to enhance the energy conversion by utilizing the low energy photons which go to waste in the conventional approach, and to curb the environmental issues for sustainable development.

Methods and Measurement System

In this study, the sample was grown by metalorganic phase epitaxy (Miyoshi et al., 1993) (with the growth of a 300 nm GaP buffer layer and a 500 nm GaPN (N: 1.87%) and GaP epitaxial layer on a (001) oriented 400 μm thick n-type GaP substrate at a temperature of 650 $^\circ\text{C}$. Trimethylgallium and phosphine were utilized as sources for Ga and P, respectively, while dimethylhydrazine was used for the nitrogen incorporation source. Gold zinc and gold germanium metal contacts were made on the top and rear of the sample using the resistance heating type vacuum evaporation system, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Sample structure of GaPN sample

Two-step photocurrent generation by the BGE light absorption were measured using TWEPC measurement system shown in Figure 2 at room temperature. Initially, we conducted external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements on both $\text{GaP}_{1-x}\text{N}_x$ and GaP, aiming to establish a comparative analysis and elucidate the absorption characteristics attributed to the band tail states. Subsequently, TWEPC measurements were conducted for each of the samples. These measurements involved employing a modulated light at 450 nm with a photon flux of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, generated by a monochromator, for the above-gap excitation (AGE) source. Additionally, we used three semiconductor lasers operating at 785 nm, 905 nm, and 980 nm, and a DPSS laser of 1342 nm. Photoluminescence (PL) measured at room temperature by a 532-nm laser are also presented in the report.

Fig. 2: Experimental two-wavelength Excitation measurement system

Results and Discussion

Figure 3 shows the EQE spectra of samples with and without nitrogen content measured at a bias voltage of 0 V for the comparison pure optical transitions taken only along with the PL spectrum of GaPN. The GaPN EQE spectrum exhibits two distinct peaks at approximately 450 nm (2.76 eV) and 590 nm (2.10 eV) respectively, while no such peaks are discernible in the sample containing no nitrogen. Therefore, the rise of two peaks is confirmed to be because of nitrogen incorporation in the sample, and consequently the optical characteristics are significantly changed the sample without nitrogen content. Each of the peaks is assigned to E^+ or direct gap transitions and E^- or quasi-direct gap transitions.

The EQE measurements depict the absorption by E^- band as well as nitrogen related band tail states below the E^- up to the measured range of EQE spectrum. However, it is worth noting that regardless of the tail states formation, the absorption by the quasi-direct gap is significantly large and was confirmed by PL measurements showing the peak at 625 nm (1.98 eV) resembling to the point of rise for the second peak in the EQE spectrum. This unique characteristic allows us to realize two-step photocurrent generation in GaPN-based solar cells using the tail states as the IB.

Fig. 3: The EQE spectra of GaPN (blue line) and GaP (black line) measured at a bias voltage of 0 V along with measured PL spectrum of GaP:N (red line).

Figure 4 shows the schematic band structure based on the EQE results and to explain the TWEPC results in the following sections. The model shows the E_+ , E_- transitions and the tail states as well as the assigned energies for the respective transitions upon dual excitation. The AGE transitions are modeled to be direct or quasi-direct transitions from VB to the E_+ or E_- band while BGE transitions are shown to be transitions from the VB to the tail states upon the first photon absorption followed by transitions from the tail states to the E_- or E_+ band by the second photon absorption. The energy of AGE light (2.76 eV) is taken to be larger than the direct gap energy (2.7 eV). On the other hand, the energy of all the BGE lights except 1342 nm (0.92 eV) was carefully chosen to be lower than that of the quasi-direct gap (1.9 eV) but higher than ~1.2 eV to which the tail states exist. Therefore, two-step transitions from VB to E_- band through tail states are likely for all BGEs except the 1342 nm light whose energy is smaller than 1.1 eV.

Fig. 4: Schematic band structure of GaPN; highlights the E_+ , E_- , and tail states assisted transitions.

Later, we conducted two-step photocurrent generation for the AGE and BGE light illumination on the sample by operating BGE and AGE light sources separately as well as in the simultaneous mode enabling us to quantitatively clarify

the effects of the BGE light illumination on the overall photocurrent density. The results of the J - V curve are illustrated in Figure 5 using the AGE light and the BGE light of 785 nm with a photon flux of $4.07 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The current densities for no light, only BGE, only AGE, and AGE with the BGE light illumination are shown by black, green, red, and blue solid lines; given as J_{Dark} , J_{BGE} , J_{AGE} , and $J_{\text{AGE+BGE}}$ respectively. The results clearly demonstrate that J_{BGE} increases in comparison to J_{Dark} by BGE light and that $J_{\text{AGE+BGE}}$ is found to be larger than J_{AGE} as shown in the inset. These findings suggest the existence of tail states in the sample considerably contributes to the absorption of BGE lights resulting in the augmentation in the two-step photocurrent generation, consequently the overall current density. Furthermore, the efficient conversion of light energy by two-step photocurrent generation process in this material system would realize a step ahead to conserve the energy (Morten et al., 2017; Esther., 2021) and reduce the loss of energy conversion. The loss is calculated to be 19% to about 50% of incident power from sun in the silicon and emerging next generation solar cells respectively (Goldschmidt et al., 2015).

Fig. 5: J - V curves show above gap excitation, below gap excitation and simultaneous illumination. The inset depicts the zoomed view above gap excitation alone and with below gap excitation.

We present the two-step photocurrent generation as a function of BGE photon flux for all the four BGEs at no bias voltage condition as in Figure 6 (a). The symbols and lines show the experimental and simulation results, respectively. J_{BGE} increases as the BGE photon flux increases for three BGE lights (785, 905, and 980 nm) by the first transition from the VB to the tail states followed by the second transition from the tail states to the E - or E + band upon the BGE light absorption while no increment could be seen by the BGE of 1342 nm. This is because the energy of BGE of 1342 nm (0.92 eV) is lower than the corresponding minimum energy for tail states (1.1 eV), and thus the transitions from the VB to the tail states are restricted as depicted in Figure 4. Consequently, the contribution to the J_{BGE} by the BGE of 1342 nm is almost zero. The enhancement by the BGE light absorption in J_{BGE} , therefore, validates the predetermined condition of two-step-two-photon absorption in the GaPN-based solar cell.

Fig. 6: J - V curves show above gap excitation, below gap excitation and simultaneous illumination. The inset depicts the zoomed view above gap excitation alone and with below gap excitation.

To make a quantitative understanding of the TWEPC results for simultaneous illumination, we define ΔJ as with respect to BGE photon flux and use it for our discussion of the results by the following expression.

$$\Delta J = J_{AGE+BGE} - J_{AGE} - J_{BGE} \quad (1)$$

The calculated results of ΔJ in Figure 6 (b) shows an increase in ΔJ as photon flux increases even for lowest energy BGE used i.e., 1342 nm. The surge in ΔJ is found to be larger than that in J_{BGE} and to tends to saturate at higher BGE photon fluxes, indicating that the nature of the increment in ΔJ is different from that in J_{BGE} . The BGE with a higher phonon energy leads to larger J_{BGE} due to higher density of tail states as could be seen from the EQE spectrum. The carrier dynamics of J_{BGE} and ΔJ is explained as; (i) J_{BGE} is observed only if the energy of applied BGE light is higher than the gap between tail states and the VB, and the increase in J_{BGE} depends on density of tail states which is found to increase up to the quasi-direct gap band edge. (ii) the AGE light with the BGE light excites electrons from VB to the $E+$ band, and the electrons relax into the IB in short time due to the short carrier lifetime and/or diffusion lengths. Therefore, the increment of ΔJ is found to be the result of re-excitation of carriers from tail states by the BGE illumination. In order to validate the qualitative explanation of obtained the experimental results using given model, a mathematical analysis was carried out for the TWEPC using governing rate equations (Kamata, 2020; Patel et al., 1991; Dai et al., 2009; Kanoh et al., 1995) based on model shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: The model used for the study of rate equations involving carrier transition and collection from the VB, IB and the CB.

The corresponding rate equations are given as:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = G_1 + G_3 - R_1 - R_3 - \frac{nv_{dn}}{d} \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = G_1 + G_2 - R_1 - R_2 - \frac{pv_{dp}}{d} \tag{3}$$

$$N_t \frac{df}{dt} = G_{IV} - G_3 - R_2 + R_3 - \frac{N_t f v_{dt}}{d}, \tag{4}$$

where

$$G_1 = \frac{(1-r_1)P_1(1-e^{-\alpha d})}{d} \tag{5}$$

$$G_2 = (1 - r_2)C_{p1}P_2N_t(1 - f) \quad (6)$$

$$G_3 = (1 - r_2)C_{n1}P_2N_t f \quad (7)$$

$$R_1 = \beta np \quad (8)$$

$$R_2 = pC_{p2}N_t f \quad (9)$$

$$R_3 = nC_{n2}N_t(1 - f). \quad (10)$$

P_1 and P_2 are the photon flux of AGE and BGE, respectively, r_1 and r_2 are the surface reflectance for AGE and BGE, β is the recombination coefficient, N_t is the tail state density, α is the absorption coefficient for AGE, f is the electron occupation function of tail states, d is layer thickness, C_{n1} and C_{p1} are the absorption rate parameters for electron and hole, respectively, while C_{n2} and C_{p2} are the capture cross section of the tail states for electron and hole, and v_{dn} , v_{dp} and v_{dt} are the drift velocities of electrons, holes, and electrons at the CB, VB, and tail states, respectively.

Thus, the governing current collection equation becomes:

$$J = nev_{dn} + N_t f ev_{dt} = pev_{dp} \quad (11)$$

The dependency of change in the current density with respect to applied BGE light was obtained for all the cases like that of experimental measurements solving the given rate equations, and the corresponding parameters are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Common parameters used for rate equation analysis.

β (cm ³ s ⁻¹)	1.5×10 ³
r_1	0.3
r_2	0.3
α (cm ⁻¹)	2.4×10 ³
C_{n2} (cm ³ s ⁻¹)	7.0×10 ⁻⁷
C_{p2} (cm ³ s ⁻¹)	7.0×10 ⁻⁷
v_{dn} (cm s ⁻¹)	4.4×10 ⁶
v_{dp} (cm s ⁻¹)	4.4×10 ⁶
v_{dt} (cm s ⁻¹)	6.3×10 ⁻⁵
N_t (cm ⁻³)	2.0×10 ¹⁶

Table 2: The BGE variables taken for the analysis.

BGE wavelength (nm)	785	905	980	1342
C_{n1} (cm ²)	2.8×10 ⁻¹⁵	1.3×10 ⁻¹⁵	7.0×10 ⁻¹⁶	4.0×10 ⁻¹⁶
C_{p1} (cm ²)	1.5×10 ⁻¹⁷	7.0×10 ⁻¹⁸	4.5×10 ⁻¹⁸	2.5×10 ⁻²⁰

The obtained results are seen to be well matching to the experimental data for all the BGE sources and for all the measured cases, as shown by solid lines in Figure 6 (a) and (b). We observed that drift velocity, v_{dt} at the tail states is extremely small than the v_{dn} and v_{dp} . We reveal that BGE light absorption increases due to the increase in electron and hole absorption rates. However, the increase in the electron absorption rate is lower than hole absorption rate.

We extended our study to see the IB state filling process for all the cases. The results demonstrate that the AGE excitation sufficiently fills up the tail states, and thus the electron occupancy approaches around 0.5. However, when the BGE is used together with the AGE, the electron occupation function begins diminishing at lower photon fluxes and eventually saturates to a value of 0.033 at higher photon fluxes as illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: The change in the tail state filling process

This reveals that higher energy excitation excited electrons from the VB to the CB relax into the IB quickly where low energy excitation excites them to the CB again thus the tail states get empty with higher BGE photon density irradiation. This occupying and emptying process of these states with the AGE and BGE results in a significant increase in the ΔJ as seen from the TWEPC measurements. In contrast, tail state occupancy remained extremely low and could get as high as approximately 0.01 even at highest photon fluxes for the BGE of 785 nm and lower for the other BGEs, thus we do not show the only BGE curves in Figure 8.

Later, we calculated the carrier relaxation time based to discuss the dynamics of carriers as:

$$\tau_n = \frac{1}{N_t C_{n2}(1-f)} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau_p = \frac{1}{N_t C_{p2}f} \quad (13)$$

and plot both electron (τ_n) and hole (τ_p) relaxation times as a function of BGE photon flux for the BGE of 785 nm with maximum photon flux of $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. As depicted in Figure 9, the electron relaxation time diminishes as the BGE photon flux increases, on other hand hole relaxation time extends to a higher value.

Fig. 9: The variation of the carrier relaxation time with respect to BGE photon flux.

This phenomenon can be attributed to the increase in empty states in the IB due to the BGE light, as previously shown in Figure 8. The reduction in electron relaxation time with BGE photon flux signifies that intermediate state occupation is believed to be a crucial factor for two-step current generation process. The calculation demonstrates that the electron lifetime decreases from 0.14 ns with no below gap excitation to 0.07 ns with the addition of low energy light at high photon fluxes. The electron relaxation time decreases by a half with dual-wavelength excitation in comparison to the only AGE excitation. These findings suggest, although the BGE light illumination increases the photocurrent density while simultaneously decreasing electron lifetime, which provides important insights for optimizing device performance.

Conclusion

In summary, the two-step photocurrent generation process was studied in GaPN (N: 1.87%) using TWEPC measurement system. The EQE spectrum showed three distinct features: (i) direct gap transitions; assigned to E_+ band (ii) quasi-direct gap transitions; assigned to E_- band, and (iii) transitions due to tail states at longer wavelengths. Notably, the study revealed the two-step photocurrent generation in GaPN by using E_- band as the CB while the band tail states as the IB, and we found that the absorption by the tail states was the key in achieving two-step photocurrent generation by two-wavelength excitation. We reproduced the experimental results with the simulation while revealing the saturation tendency in ΔJ comes from filling of intermediate states. Lastly, the results of the study indicate that BGE light illumination leads to an increase in photocurrent density and affects the carrier relaxation time. Therefore, these findings provide valuable understandings for improving the device performance.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was partially supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP19H02612.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Available upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Elliott, D. Renewable energy, and sustainable futures. *Futures*, 2000; 32, 261–2747.
- [2] Green MA, Dunlop ED, Hohl-Ebinger J, Yoshita M, Kopidakis N, Hao X. Solar cell efficiency tables (version 56). *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*. 2020;7(28):629-38.
- [3] Shockley, W., & Queisser, H. J. Detailed Balance Limit of Efficiency of p-n Junction Solar Cells. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 1961;32(3), 510-519.
- [4] Hirst, L. C., & Ekins-Daukes, N. J. Fundamental losses in solar cells. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 2011; 19(3), 286-293.
- [5] Luque, A., & Martí, A. Increasing the efficiency of ideal solar cells by photon induced transitions at intermediate levels. *Physical review letters*, 1997;78(26), 5014.
- [6] Luque, A., & Martí, A. The intermediate band solar cell: progress toward the realization of an attractive concept. *Advanced Materials*, 2010;22(2), 160-174.
- [7] Martí, A., Antolín, E., Stanley, C. R., Farmer, C. D., López, N., Díaz, P., ... & Luque, A. Production of photocurrent due to intermediate-to-conduction-band transitions: A demonstration of a key operating principle of the intermediate-band solar cell. *Physical Review Letters*, 2006;97(24), 247701.
- [8] López, N., Reichertz, L. A., Yu, K. M., Campman, K., & Walukiewicz, W. Engineering the electronic band structure for multiband solar cells. *Physical Review Letters*, 2011;106(2), 028701.
- [9] Wang, W., Lin, A. S., & Phillips, J. D. Intermediate-band photovoltaic solar cell based on ZnTe: O. *Applied Physics Letters*, 2009; 95(1).
- [10] Tanaka, T., Kin, M. Y., Levander, A. X., Dubon, O. D., Reichertz, L. A., Lopez, N., ... & Walukiewicz, W. Demonstration of ZnTe_{1-x}O_x intermediate band solar cell. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 2011;50(8R), 082304.
- [11] Tanaka, T., Miyabara, M., Nagao, Y., Saito, K., Guo, Q., Nishio, M., & Walukiewicz, W. Photogenerated current by two-step photon excitation in ZnTeO intermediate band solar cells with n-ZnO window layer. *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 2013;4(1), 196-201.
- [12] Tanaka, T., Miyabara, M., Nagao, Y., Saito, K., Guo, Q., Nishio, M., . & Walukiewicz, W. Photocurrent induced by two-photon excitation in ZnTeO intermediate band solar cells. *Applied Physics Letters*, 2013;102(5).
- [13] Zhu, Y., Asahi, S., Watanabe, K., Miyashita, N., Okada, Y., & Kita, T. Two-step excitation induced photovoltaic properties in an InAs quantum dot-in-well intermediate-band solar cell. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 2021;129(7).
- [14] Zhu, Y., Asahi, S., Miyashita, N., Okada, Y., & Kita, T. Two-photon photocurrent spectra of InAs quantum dot-in-well intermediated-band solar cells at room temperature. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 2021; 130(12).
- [15] Zhu, Y., Asahi, S., Miyashita, N., Okada, Y., & Kita, T. Two-photon photocurrent spectra of InAs quantum dot-in-well intermediated-band solar cells at room temperature. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 2021;130(12).
- [16] Raulot, J. M., Domain, C., & Guillemoles, J. F. Fe-doped CuInSe₂: An ab initio study of magnetic defects in a photovoltaic material. *Physical Review B*, 2005;71(3), 035203.
- [17] Wu, J., Walukiewicz, W., Yu, K. M., Ager III, J. W., Haller, E. E., Hong, Y. G., & Tu, C. W. Band anticrossing in GaP_{1-x}N_x alloys. *Physical Review B*, 2002;65(24), 241303.
- [18] Shan, W., Walukiewicz, W., Yu, K. M., Wu, J., Ager III, J. W., Haller, E. E., & Tu, C. W. Nature of the fundamental band gap in GaN_xP_{1-x} alloys. *Applied Physics Letters*, 2000;76(22), 3251-3253.
- [19] Chen, S., Chen, W. M., & Buyanova, I. A. Effects of strong band-tail states on exciton recombination dynamics in dilute nitride GaP/GaNP core/shell nanowires. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2018;122(33), 19212-19218.

- [20] Yaguchi, H. presented at ICPS 2022, International Conference on the Physics of Semiconductors, Sydney, 2022.
- [21] Qayoom, A., Ferdous, S., Yagi, S., & Yaguchi, H. Photocurrent enhancement by below bandgap excitation in GaPN. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 2023;62(SK), SK1038.
- [22] Miyoshi, S., Yaguchi H., Onabe K., Ito R., & Shiraki Y. Metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy of GaP_{1-x}N_x alloys on GaP. *Applied Physics Letters* 1993;63(25), 3506-3508.
- [23] Morton S, Pencheon D, Squires N. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and their implementation. *Br Med Bull.* 2017;124(1):81–90.
- [24] Andoya Esther T., *Renewable Energy and Climate Change in Developing Countries: Challenges and Adaptation.* North American Academic Research, 2021;4(6), 139-154.
- [25] Goldschmidt JC, Fischer S. Upconversion for photovoltaics—a review of materials, devices, and concepts for performance enhancement. *Advanced Optical Materials.* 2015;3(4):510-35.
- [26] Kamata, N. Spectroscopy of Nonradiative Recombination Levels by Two-Wavelength Excited Photoluminescence. *physica status solidi (b)*, 2021;258(2), 2000370.
- [27] Patel, S., Kamata, N., Kanoh, E. K. E., & Yamada, K. Y. K. Determination of the dominant nonradiative recombination parameters in heavily Si-doped GaAs/AlGaAs multiple quantum well structures. *Japanese journal of applied physics*, 1991;30(5B), L914.
- [28] Dai, Q., Schubert, M. F., Kim, M. H., Kim, J. K., Schubert, E. F., Koleske, D. D., ... & Banas, M. A. Internal quantum efficiency and nonradiative recombination coefficient of GaInN/GaN multiple quantum wells with different dislocation densities. *Applied Physics Letters*, 2009;94(11).
- [29] Kanoh, E., Hoshino, K., Kamata, N., Yamada, K., Nishioka, M., & Arakawa, Y. Saturation of photoluminescence quenching under below-gap excitation in a GaAs/AlGaAs quantum well. *Journal of luminescence*, 1995;63(5-6), 235-240.

